

ADAPTATION OF INDEPENDENT ACTIVITIES OF STUDENTS TO THE CLUSTER SYSTEM IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation: this article outlines the adaptation of independent activities of students in the educational process to the cluster system, its importance and advantages in the educational process.

Keywords: education, upbringing, Independent Education, pedagogical education innovative cluster.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada talabalarining ta'lim jarayonidagi mustaqil faoliyatini klaster tizimiga moslashtirish, uning ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyati va afzalliklari ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim, tarbiya, mustaqil ta'lim, pedagogik ta'lim innovatsion klasteri.

Аннотация: В данной статье показаны важность и преимущества адаптации самостоятельной деятельности студентов в образовательном процессе к кластерной системе.

Ключевые слова: Образование, воспитание, самостоятельное образование, инновационный кластер педагогического образования.

Today, all aspects of our life are intensely filled with news. Do not look at which area, changes in that area, cardinal turns will not attract your attention. Including, even in the educational system, there are innovations, new views, methods, methods, innovative approaches. The main goal of the education system, which is growing at an accelerated pace and is being updated, is to independently search for education recipients and develop competitive personnel who can gain interest in acquiring knowledge and have their own independent opinion, react critically and analytically to each situation. According to the requirements of the state educational standard, the task of independently searching and studying knowledge in each area is considered one of the most pressing problems of the present day. Therefore, the role of Independent Education in mastering the theoretical foundations of the sciences at the level of practical skills is incomparable [1]. It is known to all of us that the importance of the expert personnel factor in the development of the prosperity of society and the state is a vital fact that does not require proof. Large-scale reforms have been carried out and are being carried out in recent years in terms of training of specialist personnel, improving their professional quality and efficiency. In particular, special attention is paid to the content of such qualities as having an independent opinion, creativity, entrepreneurship, activity in the trained specialist personnel. J. for the organization of Independent Education in students. O. Tolipova and A. T. In the book "methodology of teaching biology" of the Gophurovs, it is necessary to compose the skills of independent and creative thinking in students. The idea that thought is human activity, the spiritual human quality that constitutes its own power, power and knowledge has been put forward [2].

The organization tasks of Independent Education in students include:

- 1) having the skills of mastering new knowledge in a thorough independent way;
- 2) searching for the necessary information, identifying convenient ways and means of learning;
- 3) effective use of information sources and addresses;
- 4) work with educational and scientific literature, regulatory documents;
- 5) work with electronic educational literature and data bank;
- 6) targeted use of the internet network;
- 7) to define a rational solution of given assignments;
- 8) database analysis;
- 9) systematic and creative approach to completing assignments;
- 10) to be able to independently receive scientific information in study rooms[3]

The history of teachings on the essence of the development of children's pedagogy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is not long of course, but among this short time, the science of pedagogy developed technologies for the successful implementation of didactics in its teachings. Among them, the "innovative cluster of pedagogical education", which is currently being interpreted in modern pedagogy, is considered an important tool for pedagogical activity. This directs the cooperation of state-owned educational institutions, various organizations, such as higher education institutions and schools, as well as their continuous activities to the effectiveness of Education. In order to carry out a cluster in the activities of an educational institution, it is necessary to pay attention mainly to the nature of its work as well. The expression of the main features of the new modern educational institution in the educational cluster is as follows:

- dynamically changing educational environment formed by scientific discoveries and new infrastructures, including new personnel, new programs, new educational technologies, new buildings and facilities, etc;
- development of education and science through the public organization of the system, network communities, media channels;
- new educational periods involving new primary education subjects;
- talented students and others who have gained high attention from birth and for life, regardless of social status;
- a new type of knowledge begins to influence, including the educational system of the country;
- regular awareness of new information;
- high attention of the state to talented youth.[4]

In conclusion, a correct and systematic approach to independent education is a guarantee of productivity in the educational system. We will achieve the expected result if we can correctly organize independent education in all branches of the system in the conditions of the innovative cluster of pedagogical education. This great homeland is all ours, it is our duty to raise its honor and status to the high. One of the areas that can make each state known to the world is the field of Education. So let's not be indifferent to education. After all, an indifferent person only keeps away from ignorance.

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